

Funded by the
European Union

Powering Europe with safe,
efficient, and sustainable
sodium-ion battery technology.

Purpose, People and Progress

ATENA+ develops advanced, sustainable, European-produced sodium-ion batteries designed to deliver high specific energy, improved cycle life, and scalable manufacturing processes. The project optimises electrochemical performance, enhances component integration, and reinforces Europe's strategic leadership in low-carbon energy storage solutions.

Project Methodology

1

Chemistry Refinement & Component Processing

Refine battery chemistry and improve components to boost performance and lifespan.

2

Pre-industrial Manufacturing & Testing

Build and test cells and modules at pre-industrial scale for reliable upscaling.

Goals & Ambitions

Environmental and Societal Impacts

Technological and Scientific Impacts

Economic and Industrial Impacts

Develop and optimise high-performance NIBs

Improve battery chemistry and components for better performance and durability.

Ensure environmental and social sustainability

Reduce environmental impact and promote ethical, socially responsible practices.

Prove pre-industrial manufacturing feasibility

Demonstrate reliable processes for manufacturing at pre-industrial scale.

Establish a fully European battery value chain

Build an EU-based supply chain covering materials, production, and assembly.

Boost adoption and innovation dissemination

Support faster rollout and sharing of innovative technologies across markets.

3

Tech Validation & Virtual Upscaling

Validate technologies and digitally simulate large-scale production environments.

4

Environmental, Social & Techno-Economic Assessment

Assess environmental, social and economic impacts of battery development and production.

5

Outreach Strategy & Road-to-Market

Plan pathways to market and implement dissemination of project results and innovations.

ATENA+ Empowers Battery Innovation

Sodium-Ion
Batteries

High Performance
Batteries

Made
in Europe

Consortium

TOPSOE

SEEL

ICONS

Engreen

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